

Dyonic Black Holes in Lorentz-Violating Gravity with a Background Kalb-Ramond Field: Quasiperiodic Oscillations and Radiative Properties

Faizuddin Ahmed^{1,*}, Ahmad Al-Badawi^{2,†} and Edilberto O Silva^{3,‡}

¹*Department of Physics, The Assam Royal Global University, Guwahati, 781035, Assam, India*

²*Department of Physics, Al-Hussein Bin Talal University 71111, Ma'an, Jordan*

³*Programa de Pós-Graduação em Física & Coordenação do Curso de Física – Bacharelado, Universidade Federal do Maranhão, 65085-580 São Luís, Maranhão, Brazil*

In this paper, we investigate particle dynamics around dyonic black holes in Kalb–Ramond gravity, with particular emphasis on the circular motion of neutral test particles. Using the effective-potential formalism, we analyze the quasiperiodic oscillation (QPO) fundamental frequencies and discuss how they are influenced by the black-hole geometric parameters. We then study the sparsity of Hawking radiation and the associated spectral energy-emission rate, highlighting deviations from the standard Schwarzschild scenario. Our analysis shows that the electric charge, the magnetic charge, and the Lorentz-violating Kalb–Ramond parameter modify the location of circular orbits, the epicyclic frequencies, the Hawking sparsity, and the radiative emission profile of the considered black-hole solution.

Keywords: Modified gravity; black holes; geodesics; QPOs; Hawking radiation

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the most promising observational tools for probing the physical processes in the vicinity of black-hole candidates is the study of quasi-periodic oscillations (QPOs) in the X-ray power density spectra of microquasars [1]. In this context, QPOs provide a valuable astrophysical window into the strong-gravity regime, offering significant support for testing the validity of gravitational models under extreme conditions. Theoretical frameworks employed to explain these observational features often involve epicyclic motion, where radial and vertical epicyclic frequencies govern the oscillatory behavior of neutral test particles orbiting a black hole [2–5]. In addition, the dynamics of charged particles in magnetized or electrically charged backgrounds further enrich the possible mechanisms responsible for QPO generation [6, 7].

In low-mass X-ray binary (LMXB) systems containing either a neutron star (NS) or a black hole, QPOs appear as distinct peaks in the power density spectrum. They are broadly classified into low-frequency (LF) QPOs, typically in the range of 0.1–30 Hz, and high-frequency (HF) QPOs, occurring approximately in the range of 40–450 Hz. These oscillations are commonly attributed to relativistic effects such as Lense–Thirring precession, epicyclic motion, and nonlinear resonance phenomena occurring in the innermost regions of the accretion disk. When HF QPOs appear in pairs, they are referred to as twin-peak HF QPOs, which are of particular interest due to their potential to constrain the fundamental parameters of compact objects, such as mass and spin. LF QPOs are generally strong, stable, and exhibit significant frequency variability, whereas HF QPOs are typically weaker, less stable, and show relatively small frequency drifts. Despite these differences, both types of

QPOs can coexist in certain X-ray binary systems, indicating the presence of multiple oscillatory mechanisms operating simultaneously in different regions of the accretion flow. Astrophysical studies suggest that LF and HF QPOs originate from distinct regions of the accretion disk, reflecting different physical processes governing disk dynamics. Consequently, a variety of theoretical models have been proposed to explain the origin and behavior of QPOs, including resonance models, disk-oscillation models, and relativistic precession frameworks [8–11]. Interesting work on QPOs has recently been reported in [12–19].

The observational era of black-hole physics has undergone a remarkable transformation with the groundbreaking achievements of the Event Horizon Telescope Collaboration, which produced the first direct images of black-hole shadows [20–25]. These historic observations opened an unprecedented window into the strong-field regime of gravity near the event horizon, providing an exceptional opportunity to test the predictions of general relativity and to explore possible deviations arising from alternative theories of gravity. The shadow cast by a black hole encodes crucial information about the geometry of spacetime, the nature of photon trajectories, and the properties of the compact object itself, thereby making black-hole imaging an important tool in modern gravitational physics and astrophysics. Moreover, the direct detection of gravitational waves by the LIGO–Virgo–KAGRA Collaborations [26–28] has provided strong observational evidence in support of Einstein’s general theory of relativity. The measured waveforms from merging compact objects have shown remarkable agreement with theoretical predictions, thereby confirming the validity of general relativity in the highly dynamical and strong-gravity regime. These observations have inaugurated the era of gravitational-wave astronomy, enabling detailed studies of black holes, neutron stars, and alternative theories of gravity, while also offering new opportunities to probe the fundamental properties of spacetime.

Although the observational confirmation of black-hole shadows is recent, the theoretical foundation of this

* faizuddinahmed15@gmail.com

† ahmadbadawi@ahu.edu.jo

‡ edilberto.silva@ufma.br (Corresponding author)

phenomenon dates back several decades. Early investigations by John Lighton Synge demonstrated how light propagates in curved spacetime and established the basis for understanding optical phenomena around compact objects [29]. Subsequently, the pioneering work of Bardeen and collaborators provided a detailed analysis of photon motion and the appearance of black holes in Schwarzschild and Kerr geometries [30]. In the case of a Schwarzschild black hole, photons can orbit the black hole on an unstable circular trajectory known as the photon sphere, located at a radius $r_s = 3M$, where M denotes the mass of the black hole. The corresponding shadow radius observed at infinity is given by $R_{\text{sh}} = 3\sqrt{3}M$. Since then, extensive studies of black-hole shadows have been carried out for a wide variety of black-hole solutions in general relativity as well as in numerous modified theories of gravity, revealing rich phenomenological features and offering new avenues for testing gravitational theories through astrophysical observations.

Lorentz symmetry is one of the fundamental pillars of modern physics, forming the basis of both general relativity (GR) and the Standard Model of elementary particles. It ensures that the laws of physics remain invariant under rotations and boosts between inertial reference frames. Despite its central importance, considerable attention has been devoted to investigating the possible limits of Lorentz invariance and the consequences of Lorentz symmetry breaking (LSB). Interest in this subject increased significantly following the pioneering work of V. Alan Kostelecký and collaborators [31], where small deviations from exact Lorentz symmetry were explored within the framework of string theory. Their work suggested that Lorentz symmetry might be spontaneously broken at high-energy scales, motivating extensive studies of Lorentz-violating effects in particle physics, gravitation, and cosmology.

In the context of field theory, Lorentz symmetry breaking has been systematically formulated through the framework of the Standard Model Extension (SME), which is an effective field theory incorporating all possible Lorentz- and CPT-violating terms consistent with coordinate independence [32–36]. The SME provides a unified and comprehensive approach for investigating Lorentz violation in both the Standard Model and gravitational sectors. An important feature of the SME is that gauge symmetry remains preserved even in the presence of Lorentz-violating background fields. Within this framework, simple yet physically rich Lorentz-violating gravitational models can be constructed by introducing self-interacting vector or tensor fields that acquire nonzero vacuum expectation values. Among the most widely studied examples is the Einstein-bumblebee gravity model, where a vector field, known as the bumblebee field, couples nonminimally to the Ricci tensor and induces spontaneous Lorentz symmetry breaking. Another important extension involves antisymmetric tensor fields, such as the Kalb–Ramond field, which also lead to modified gravitational dynamics and novel spacetime structures.

Bumblebee gravity and theories involving Kalb–Ramond fields have been extensively investigated in recent years. Several studies have explored the effects of Lorentz violation

on black-hole physics, gravitational lensing, quasinormal modes, thermodynamics, and compact astrophysical objects [37–56]. In particular, these theories provide compelling frameworks for examining gravitational systems both in the absence and presence of topological defects, such as global monopoles and cosmic strings. The spontaneous breaking of Lorentz symmetry through vector or tensor fields enriches the theoretical structure of modified gravity and gives rise to new black-hole solutions with distinct geometrical and observational properties. Such modifications can significantly affect photon trajectories, spacetime horizons, and black-hole shadows, thereby offering potential observational signatures that may be tested through current and future astrophysical observations. Recently, Lin et al. [57] constructed a dyonic black-hole solution in Lorentz-violating gravity with a background Kalb–Ramond field. They investigated the photon sphere, the black-hole shadow, the innermost stable circular orbit, and thermodynamic properties in the extended phase space. In the present work, we focus on the static sector with vanishing cosmological constant/pressure contribution and write the geometry in standard Schwarzschild-like coordinates as [57]

$$ds^2 = -f(r) dt^2 + \frac{dr^2}{f(r)} + r^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2), \quad (1)$$

where the lapse function is

$$f(r) = \frac{1}{1-\ell} - \frac{2M}{r} + \frac{Q^2}{(1-\ell)^2 r^2} + \frac{P^2}{(1-2\ell)r^2}, \quad (2)$$

in which M is the black-hole mass, Q is the electric charge, P is the magnetic charge, and ℓ is the dimensionless Kalb–Ramond Lorentz-violating parameter. We denote the magnetic charge by P in order to avoid confusion with the canonical momentum p_μ . Lorentz-violating effects are characterized by the parameter ℓ in this spacetime, whose value is constrained to be very small [44]. The parameter domain must also be restricted by $1-\ell > 0$, $1-2\ell > 0$, and by the horizon-existence condition derived below. Although phenomenological constraints suggest very small values of ℓ , we use an enlarged interval of ℓ in the figures to make the parameter dependence visually manifest; the physically constrained regime is contained in the small- ℓ portion of the curves. In the limit $P \rightarrow 0$, one recovers the electrically charged black hole in Kalb–Ramond gravity [43], while in the limit $Q \rightarrow 0$ and $P \rightarrow 0$, one recovers a static uncharged black hole in Kalb–Ramond gravity [44].

The main motivation of this work is to investigate several important physical properties of dyonic black holes in Lorentz-violating gravity that have not yet been thoroughly explored in the existing literature. In particular, although both uncharged and charged black-hole solutions in Lorentz-violating gravity have been obtained previously, a detailed analysis of particle dynamics and quasiperiodic-oscillation frequencies in the genuinely dyonic case, where both electric and magnetic charges are present, is still lacking. Another important aspect that remains comparatively unexplored is the behavior of Hawking radiation, especially the sparsity

of the radiation and the corresponding spectral energy-emission rate in the presence of electric charge, magnetic charge, and Lorentz-violating effects. Motivated by these gaps, we provide a focused analysis of the dynamical and radiative properties of the dyonic black hole in Kalb–Ramond gravity and clarify how the parameters Q , P , and ℓ modify these physical observables when compared with the standard Schwarzschild scenario.

II. EQUATION OF MOTION

Throughout the analytical derivations we use geometrized units $G = c = \hbar = k_B = 1$, unless otherwise stated. Using the general Hamiltonian formalism, we describe the dynamics of a neutral particle of rest mass m in the vicinity of the selected black hole. The geodesic equations of motion can be found using the standard Hamilton–Jacobi (H-J) method. The H-J action function S fulfills the H-J equation

$$-m^2 = -\frac{1}{f(r)} \left(\frac{\partial S}{\partial t} \right)^2 + f(r) \left(\frac{\partial S}{\partial r} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{r^2} \left(\frac{\partial S}{\partial \theta} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin^2 \theta} \left(\frac{\partial S}{\partial \phi} \right)^2. \quad (3)$$

The action function S is connected to the test-particle four-momentum by the relation $p_\mu \equiv \partial S / \partial x^\mu$. We assume the standard separated form of the action function, $S \equiv -Et + S_r(r) + S_\theta(\theta) + L\phi$. Because the spacetime is spherically symmetric, the particle motion can be restricted without loss of generality to the equatorial plane, $\theta = \pi/2$. Stationarity and axial symmetry imply the conserved covariant energy $E \equiv -p_t$ and the conserved azimuthal angular momentum $L \equiv p_\phi$, respectively.

The Hamiltonian of a neutral particle of mass m using spacetime (1) is given by [58–60]

$$\mathbb{H} = \frac{1}{2} g^{\mu\nu} p_\mu p_\nu + \frac{m^2}{2},$$

where $p^\mu = mu^\mu$ represents the four-momentum, and $u^\mu = dx^\mu/d\tau$ indicates the four-velocity.

One way to express the Hamilton equations of motion is as

$$\frac{dx^\mu}{d\zeta} \equiv mu^\mu = \frac{\partial H}{\partial p_\mu}, \quad \frac{dp_\mu}{d\zeta} = -\frac{\partial H}{\partial x^\mu}, \quad (4)$$

where $\zeta = \tau/m$ represents the affine parameter and τ is the test particle's proper time.

Since the metric coefficients do not explicitly depend on time t and azimuthal angle ϕ , there are two constants of motion expressed as follows:

$$E/m = \mathcal{E} = f(r) \left(\frac{dt}{d\tau} \right), \quad (5)$$

$$L/m = \mathcal{L} = r^2 \sin^2 \theta \left(\frac{d\phi}{d\tau} \right), \quad (6)$$

where \mathcal{E} and \mathcal{L} are, respectively, the particle energy and the angular momentum per unit mass.

Therefore, the Hamiltonian can be expressed as

$$\mathbb{H} = \frac{p_r^2}{2} f(r) + \frac{p_\theta^2}{2r^2} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{m^2}{f(r)} (U_{\text{eff}}(r, \theta) - \mathcal{E}^2), \quad (7)$$

where the effective potential of the system is given by

$$U_{\text{eff}}(r, \theta) = \left(1 + \frac{\mathcal{L}^2}{r^2 \sin^2 \theta} \right) f(r). \quad (8)$$

The effective potential U_{eff} depends on key spacetime parameters, including the electric charge Q , magnetic charge P , Kalb–Ramond parameter ℓ , and mass M , which collectively govern the motion of test particles. This potential provides a powerful framework for analyzing particle trajectories without directly solving the equations of motion. In relativistic black-hole spacetimes, extrema of U_{eff} determine circular orbits: local minima correspond to stable circular motion, whereas local maxima correspond to unstable circular motion. The transition between these two regimes defines the marginally stable orbit and is therefore central to the ISCO analysis.

The ISCO can be ascertained by implementing the pertinent criteria[61]

$$U_{\text{eff}}(r_c, \pi/2) = \mathcal{E}_c^2, \quad \left. \frac{dU_{\text{eff}}}{dr} \right|_{r=r_c} = 0, \quad \left. \frac{d^2 U_{\text{eff}}}{dr^2} \right|_{r=r_c} = 0. \quad (9)$$

Solving the first two conditions yields the specific energy and angular momentum of a test particle orbiting in a circular path,

$$\mathcal{E}_c^2 = \frac{2f_c^2}{2f_c - r_c f'_c}, \quad (10)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_c^2 = \frac{r_c^3 f'_c}{2f_c - r_c f'_c}, \quad (11)$$

where $f_c = f(r_c)$ and $f'_c = f'(r_c)$. These expressions are meaningful when $2f_c - r_c f'_c > 0$ and $\mathcal{E}_c^2, \mathcal{L}_c^2 > 0$.

The innermost stable circular orbit (ISCO) is obtained from the marginal-stability condition, expressed as follows:

$$f(r_{\text{ISCO}})f''(r_{\text{ISCO}}) - 2[f'(r_{\text{ISCO}})]^2 + \frac{3f(r_{\text{ISCO}})f'(r_{\text{ISCO}})}{r_{\text{ISCO}}} = 0. \quad (12)$$

Figure 1 displays the effective potential for both positive and negative values of the Lorentz-violating parameter. In all panels the curves are shown only in the exterior region of the corresponding event horizon. This restriction is important because the potential has a direct orbital interpretation only outside r_+ . For the positive branch, increasing ℓ raises the potential barrier and changes the asymptotic level through the factor $1/(1 - \ell)$. For the negative branch, the opposite trend is observed, since the asymptotic value of the lapse function decreases when $\ell < 0$. Thus, even before imposing the circular-orbit conditions, the effective potential already shows that the Kalb–Ramond parameter modifies the allowed radial domain and the binding properties of timelike trajectories.

FIG. 1. Effective potential U_{eff} for neutral massive test particles in the dyonic Kalb–Ramond black-hole spacetime. The black-hole parameters are fixed as $Q/M = P/M = 0.25$ and the particle angular momentum is $\mathcal{L}/M = 1$. Panel (a) shows the scan over positive Lorentz-violating parameter values, $0 \leq \ell \leq 0.40$, whereas panel (b) shows the negative branch, $-0.50 \leq \ell \leq 0$. The curves are masked inside the corresponding event horizon and therefore represent only the exterior black-hole region. The figure illustrates how ℓ changes both the near-horizon rise of the potential and its large-radius normalization.

A. Particle Trajectory and Effective Force

Next, we focus on the particle trajectory in the given gravitational field and show how geometric parameters influence the particle motion. The equation of orbit is obtained as

$$\frac{dr}{d\phi} = \pm r^2 \left[\frac{\mathcal{E}^2}{\mathcal{L}^2} - \left(\frac{1}{\mathcal{L}^2} + \frac{1}{r^2} \right) \left(\frac{1}{1-\ell} - \frac{2M}{r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \left[\frac{Q^2}{(1-\ell)^2} + \frac{P^2}{1-2\ell} \right] \right) \right]^{1/2}. \quad (13)$$

Transforming to a new variable via $u(\phi) = 1/r(\phi)$, we obtain

$$\frac{du}{d\phi} = \pm \left[\frac{\mathcal{E}^2}{\mathcal{L}^2} - \left(\frac{1}{\mathcal{L}^2} + u^2 \right) \left(\frac{1}{1-\ell} - 2Mu + u^2 \left[\frac{Q^2}{(1-\ell)^2} + \frac{P^2}{1-2\ell} \right] \right) \right]^{1/2} \equiv \Phi(u). \quad (14)$$

We observe that the particle trajectory depends on Q , P , ℓ , as well as on the particle energy and angular momentum. The equation $\Phi(u) = 0$ determines the radial turning points of the orbit. The complete trajectory is obtained by integrating Eq. (14) with the chosen initial position r_i and the corresponding initial sign of $du/d\phi$.

The effective force acting on a particle provides a clear description of its motion, indicating whether it is attracted toward or repelled from the black hole (BH). We consider the dynamics of test particles in the vicinity of a static black hole, where both attractive and repulsive gravitational effects may arise depending on the spacetime parameters and particle properties. The effective force acting on the particle is defined as the negative gradient of the effective potential U_{eff} , given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F} &= -\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial U_{\text{eff}}}{\partial r} \\ &= -\frac{1}{r} \left(\frac{M}{r} - \frac{1}{r^2} \left(\frac{Q^2}{(1-\ell)^2} + \frac{P^2}{1-2\ell} \right) \right) \\ &\quad + \frac{\mathcal{L}^2}{r^3} \left(\frac{1}{1-\ell} - \frac{3M}{r} + \frac{2}{r^2} \left(\frac{Q^2}{(1-\ell)^2} + \frac{P^2}{1-2\ell} \right) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

The corresponding effective radial force is shown in Fig. 2. Since $\mathcal{F} = -(1/2)\partial U_{\text{eff}}/\partial r$, its sign and magnitude encode the radial tendency of the effective-potential profile. For the parameter values used in the figure, the force is predominantly attractive in the exterior region and approaches zero from below at large radius. Increasing ℓ makes the near-horizon attraction stronger and shifts the steep part of the force profile toward smaller radii, consistently with the reduction of r_+ along the positive- ℓ branch.

The effect of the same parameters on characteristic orbital radii and representative particle trajectories is summarized

FIG. 2. Effective radial force $M\mathcal{F}$ experienced by a neutral massive test particle as a function of r/M . The parameters are fixed as $Q/M = P/M = 0.25$ and $\mathcal{L}/M = 1$, while the color scale denotes $0 \leq \ell \leq 0.40$. The dashed horizontal line marks $\mathcal{F} = 0$. The curves are plotted only outside the event horizon, showing that the force becomes increasingly negative close to the black hole and rapidly tends to zero in the weak-field regime.

in Fig. 3. Panel (a) shows that, for the fixed charges used in the scan, the event horizon, photon sphere, and ISCO decrease as ℓ increases. This behavior reflects the combined influence of the global normalization of $f(r)$ and the charge terms weighted by $(1 - \ell)^{-2}$ and $(1 - 2\ell)^{-1}$. Panels (b) and (c) isolate the role of the electric and magnetic charges at fixed ℓ : in both cases, increasing the charge decreases the ISCO radius, indicating that stable circular orbits can move closer to the horizon in the charged geometry. Panel (d) gives representative integrated trajectories, showing that the Lorentz-violating parameter changes the amount of azimuthal winding and the radial excursion of the orbit.

B. Harmonic Oscillations as Perturbations of Circular Orbits

To examine the oscillatory motion of neutral particles, we apply perturbations to the equations of motion around stable circular orbits. Upon a small displacement from its equilibrium position in the equatorial plane, a test particle experiences epicyclic motion, which, in the linear regime, is described by harmonic oscillations.

The orbital angular velocity of test particles in circular orbits, with respect to the coordinate time t adopted in Eq. (1), is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_\phi &= \frac{d\phi}{dt} = \sqrt{\frac{f'(r)}{2r}} \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{M}{r^3} - \frac{Q^2}{(1-\ell)^2 r^4} - \frac{P^2}{(1-2\ell)r^4}}. \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

All angular frequencies in Eqs. (16)–(22) are dimensionless in geometrized units. To express them in Hz for a black

hole of mass M , one must use the linear conversion factor $c^3/(2\pi GM)$. Here, we take the speed of light as $c = 3 \times 10^8 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ and the Newtonian gravitational constant as $G = 6.67 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-2}$. Because $f(r) \rightarrow 1/(1 - \ell)$ at large r , frequencies normalized with respect to a unit timelike Killing vector at infinity acquire an additional factor $\sqrt{1 - \ell}$. Unless explicitly stated otherwise, we keep the same coordinate-time normalization used in the metric.

The test particles orbiting a black hole along stable circular orbits may oscillate in the radial and vertical directions due to small displacements $r \rightarrow r + \delta r$ and $\theta \rightarrow \pi/2 + \delta\theta$. The frequencies of radial and vertical oscillations can be evaluated from [62, 63]

$$\frac{d^2}{dt^2}(\delta r) + \Omega_r^2 \delta r = 0, \quad (17)$$

$$\frac{d^2}{dt^2}(\delta\theta) + \Omega_\theta^2 \delta\theta = 0, \quad (18)$$

where [12, 13]

$$\Omega_r^2 = - \frac{1}{2g_{rr}(u^t)^2} \left. \frac{d^2 U_{\text{eff}}}{dr^2} \right|_{r=r_c, \theta=\pi/2}, \quad (19)$$

$$\Omega_\theta^2 = - \frac{1}{2g_{\theta\theta}g^{rr}(u^t)^2} \left. \frac{d^2 U_{\text{eff}}}{d\theta^2} \right|_{r=r_c, \theta=\pi/2} \quad (20)$$

are the radial and vertical epicyclic frequencies, respectively, in the coordinate-time normalization adopted above.

In our case, these frequencies become

$$\Omega_r^2 = \frac{1}{2} \left[f(r) f''(r) - 2 (f'(r))^2 + \frac{3f(r) f'(r)}{r} \right], \quad (21)$$

$$\Omega_\theta^2 = \Omega_\phi^2. \quad (22)$$

The radial epicyclic frequency in Eq. (21) correctly reduces to $\Omega_r^2 = Mr^{-3}(1 - 6M/r)$ in the Schwarzschild limit $Q = P = \ell = 0$, while Eq. (22) follows from spherical symmetry. Stable circular orbits require $\Omega_r^2 \geq 0$, and the ISCO is located by $\Omega_r^2 = 0$.

Furthermore, to express the frequencies in Hz we use

$$\begin{cases} \nu_{\phi,r,\theta} = \frac{c^3}{2\pi GM} \Omega_{\phi,r,\theta}, \\ \frac{c^3}{2\pi GM} \approx 3.235 \times 10^4 \left(\frac{M_\odot}{M} \right) \text{ Hz}. \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

The corrected radial and azimuthal frequencies are plotted in Fig. 4. The radial frequency vanishes at the ISCO and is real only in the stable region, which is why each curve starts at a different minimum radius. It then reaches a maximum and decays in the weak-field limit. In contrast, the azimuthal frequency decreases monotonically with radius and is only weakly affected by ℓ at large distances. The separation between ν_ϕ and ν_r is the source of periastron precession and is therefore essential for QPO models based on relativistic precession.

FIG. 3. Geodesic and circular-orbit diagnostics for the dyonic Kalb–Ramond black hole. Panel (a) shows the event-horizon radius r_+ , the photon-sphere radius r_{ph} , and the ISCO radius r_{ISCO} as functions of ℓ for $Q/M = P/M = 0.25$. Panel (b) displays r_{ISCO}/M as a function of the electric charge Q/M at fixed $P/M = 0.25$ and $\ell = 0.10$. Panel (c) displays r_{ISCO}/M as a function of the magnetic charge P/M at fixed $Q/M = 0.25$ and $\ell = 0.10$. Panel (d) shows representative equatorial particle trajectories obtained by integrating Eq. (14) for $Q/M = P/M = 0.25$ and $\mathcal{L}/M = 4.20$, with the color scale denoting ℓ . These plots complement the effective-potential analysis by showing how the allowed orbital region and the orbit morphology respond to electric charge, magnetic charge, and Lorentz violation.

For local measurements by a comoving observer, one may relate the coordinate-time frequencies to proper-time frequencies through the redshift factor $u^t = dt/d\tau$. Thus,

$$\omega_i^{\text{loc}} = \Omega_i u^t, \quad u^t = \frac{dt}{d\tau} = \frac{\mathcal{E}}{f(r)} \quad (i = r, \theta, \phi). \quad (24)$$

In the numerical plots below, however, we use the coordinate-time frequencies converted to Hz by Eq. (23).

The periastron (or apsidal) precession frequency describes the slow rotation of the point of closest approach in a bound orbit around a compact object. In general relativistic orbital motion, a test particle does not trace a closed ellipse;

instead, the orbit exhibits a precession due to the difference between the azimuthal and radial oscillation rates. This behavior is characterized by two fundamental frequencies: the azimuthal (orbital) frequency Ω_ϕ , which governs the angular motion of the particle, and the radial epicyclic frequency Ω_r , which describes small oscillations of the particle in the radial direction about a circular orbit.

Because these two frequencies are not equal in curved spacetime, the orbit fails to close after one radial period, leading to a shift in the location of the periastron. The rate of this shift defines the periastron precession frequency,

FIG. 4. Fundamental QPO frequencies for a black hole with astrophysical mass $M_{\text{BH}} = 10 M_{\odot}$ and charges $Q/M = P/M = 0.25$. Panel (a) shows the radial epicyclic frequency ν_r obtained from the corrected expression in Eq. (21). The small markers on the horizontal axis indicate the ISCO positions, where $\nu_r = 0$. Panel (b) shows the azimuthal frequency, which coincides with the vertical epicyclic frequency, $\nu_{\phi} = \nu_{\theta}$, due to spherical symmetry. The color scale corresponds to $0 \leq \ell \leq 0.20$. The frequencies are converted to Hz using the linear relation in Eq. (23).

commonly written as

$$\Omega_p = \Omega_{\phi} - \Omega_r, \quad \Omega_r = \sqrt{\Omega_r^2}, \quad (25)$$

for stable orbits with $\Omega_r^2 \geq 0$. Some conventions may interchange the order of subtraction, but physically the observable precession rate is taken as the positive difference between the azimuthal and radial frequencies. In the Newtonian limit, $\Omega_r = \Omega_{\phi}$, so the precession vanishes and closed Keplerian orbits are recovered, whereas in general relativity $\Omega_r < \Omega_{\phi}$, resulting in a forward precession of the orbit. In astrophysical applications such as quasiperiodic oscillations (QPOs), the periastron precession frequency plays an important role.

The resulting periastron-precession frequency is shown in Fig. 5. Because $\nu_p = \nu_{\phi} - \nu_r$, the precession is largest in the strong-field region close to the ISCO and decreases rapidly as the orbit moves outward. The Lorentz-violating parameter affects ν_p both by shifting the ISCO radius and by modifying the difference between the azimuthal and radial epicyclic frequencies.

III. SPARSITY OF HAWKING RADIATION

We now quantify the sparsity of Hawking radiation for the selected black-hole solution. Although black holes radiate thermally with a temperature determined by the surface gravity—closely resembling ideal black bodies—the Hawking emission process is inherently discrete in time, consisting of well-separated quantum events rather than a

FIG. 5. Periastron-precession frequency $\nu_p = \nu_{\phi} - \nu_r$ as a function of r/M for $Q/M = P/M = 0.25$ and $M_{\text{BH}} = 10 M_{\odot}$. The color scale denotes $0 \leq \ell \leq 0.20$. Only the region with real radial epicyclic frequency is shown. The curves demonstrate that relativistic precession is enhanced close to the compact object and becomes negligible in the weak-field region.

continuous flux. The sparsity parameter characterizes this feature by measuring the average time between successive emissions, normalized by an intrinsic energy-dependent timescale. It is constructed by comparing the squared thermal wavelength $\lambda_t = 2\pi/T$ with the effective radiating area A_{eff}

FIG. 6. Existence domain of the event horizon in the electric–magnetic charge plane. The panels correspond to (a) $\ell = 0$, (b) $\ell = 0.10$, (c) $\ell = 0.20$, and (d) $\ell = 0.30$. The green region satisfies the corrected horizon condition $M^2 - Q^2/(1 - \ell)^3 - P^2/[(1 - \ell)(1 - 2\ell)] \geq 0$, while the blue region violates it. The boundary curve is the extremal black-hole limit. The progressive reduction of the green region shows that positive Lorentz violation tightens the allowed range of electric and magnetic charges.

[64–67]:

$$\psi = \frac{\mathcal{C}}{\tilde{g}} \left(\frac{\lambda_t^2}{A_{\text{eff}}} \right), \quad (26)$$

where \mathcal{C} is a dimensionless constant and \tilde{g} denotes the spin-degeneracy factor of the emitted particle species. The effective radiating area is given by $A_{\text{eff}} = \frac{27}{4} A_{\text{BH}}$, while T represents the Hawking temperature of the black hole. In the following we set $\mathcal{C}/\tilde{g} = 1$, so that the Schwarzschild reference value follows directly from the same definitions, $\lambda_t = 2\pi/T_{\text{Sch}}$ and $A_{\text{eff}} = 27A_{\text{BH}}/4$. A shadow-based effective area, $A_{\text{eff}} \sim \sigma_{\text{lim}} \simeq \pi R_{\text{sh}}^2$ [68], can also be used for a fully geometry-dependent estimate; the two prescriptions should not be mixed without specifying the approximation.

The surface gravity associated with the coordinate-time Killing vector is [69, 70]

$$\kappa = \frac{f'(r_h)}{2}, \quad T = \frac{\kappa}{2\pi} = \frac{f'(r_h)}{4\pi}. \quad (27)$$

Thus, with the same time normalization used in Eq. (1), the Hawking temperature is

$$T = \frac{f'(r_h)}{4\pi} = \frac{1}{4\pi r_h} \left(\frac{1}{1 - \ell} - \frac{1}{r_h^2} \left(\frac{Q^2}{(1 - \ell)^2} + \frac{P^2}{(1 - 2\ell)} \right) \right), \quad (28)$$

FIG. 7. Thermodynamic and radiative properties for $Q/M = P/M = 0.25$. Panel (a) shows the Hawking temperature T as a function of ℓ , using the coordinate-time normalization of Eq. (27). Panel (b) shows the sparsity ratio ψ/ψ_{Sch} obtained from Eq. (31), with $\psi_{\text{Sch}} = 64\pi^3/27$. Panel (c) shows the shadow radius R_{sh}/M computed from Eqs. (34) and (35). Panel (d) shows the spectral energy-emission rate $d^2\mathbb{E}/(d\omega dt)$ as a function of the dimensionless frequency $M\omega$ for representative values of ℓ in the interval $0 \leq \ell \leq 0.40$. The figure illustrates how the same geometric deformation profile controls the Hawking temperature, the discreteness of the emission process, the optical shadow size, and the high-frequency emission profile.

where we have used the relation

$$M = \frac{r_h}{2(1-\ell)} + \frac{1}{2r_h} \left(\frac{Q^2}{(1-\ell)^2} + \frac{P^2}{(1-2\ell)} \right). \quad (29)$$

If the timelike Killing vector is normalized to unit norm at infinity, one obtains $T_\infty = \sqrt{1-\ell}T$.

The black-hole horizons are obtained from $f(r) = 0$ and

are given by

$$r_\pm = (1-\ell) \times \left(M \pm \sqrt{M^2 - \frac{Q^2}{(1-\ell)^3} - \frac{P^2}{(1-\ell)(1-2\ell)}} \right). \quad (30)$$

The event horizon is $r_h = r_+$, and the extremal limit follows from the vanishing of the square root in Eq. (30).

The corresponding horizon-existence domain is displayed in Fig. 6. The green region represents parameter values for which the discriminant in Eq. (30) is nonnegative and the

geometry contains an event horizon, while the blue region corresponds to horizonless configurations. As ℓ increases, the allowed region in the $(Q/M, P/M)$ plane shrinks. This behavior is expected from Eq. (30), because the electric and magnetic charge contributions are weighted by factors that grow with ℓ . Consequently, numerical scans over Q/M , P/M , and ℓ must be restricted to the green region in order to describe black holes rather than naked horizonless configurations.

With these, the sparsity parameter is obtained as

$$\psi = \left[\frac{1}{1-\ell} - \frac{1}{r_h^2} \left\{ \frac{Q^2}{(1-\ell)^2} + \frac{P^2}{(1-2\ell)} \right\} \right]^{-2} \psi_{\text{Sch}}, \quad (31)$$

where $\psi_{\text{Sch}} = \frac{64\pi^3}{27} \approx 73.5$ is the sparsity parameter for the standard Schwarzschild black hole and $r_h = r_+$ is the horizon radius given in Eq. (30). Equation (31) shows explicitly that electric charge, magnetic charge, and Lorentz violation affect the sparsity both directly through the temperature factor and indirectly through the corrected horizon radius.

IV. ENERGY EMISSION RATE

Quantum fluctuations in curved spacetime play a central role in black-hole thermodynamics and quantum field theory in strong gravitational backgrounds. Near the event horizon, vacuum fluctuations continuously generate particle–antiparticle pairs. In the presence of the horizon, these virtual pairs can be separated: one particle may tunnel through the gravitational potential barrier and escape to infinity, while its partner with negative energy, as measured relative to infinity, is effectively absorbed by the black hole. This semiclassical tunneling picture provides an intuitive description of Hawking radiation, first proposed by Stephen Hawking [69], and explains how black holes can emit thermal radiation despite their strong gravitational fields. As a consequence of this quantum emission process, the black hole gradually loses mass over time. The continuous outflow of energy in the form of Hawking radiation leads to a slow but steady decrease in the black-hole mass and horizon area, ultimately suggesting that an isolated black hole can completely evaporate after a sufficiently long time. The evaporation rate is directly related to the energy flux carried away by the emitted particles and depends on the black-hole temperature, which increases as the mass decreases. Several researchers have studied the energy emission rate in various black-hole configurations and analyzed the results (see Refs. [71–74]).

From the perspective of a distant observer, the dynamics of high-energy particle absorption by the black hole can be characterized through the absorption or capture cross section. In the high-frequency limit, this cross section exhibits oscillatory behavior around a constant limiting value, σ_{lim} , which is closely connected to the properties of unstable photon orbits and the geometry of the photon sphere [75–77]. Remarkably, this limiting cross section is directly related to the optical appearance of the black hole and can be interpreted as being associated with the observed shadow radius of the

black hole [68]. The limiting absorption cross section is estimated as

$$\sigma_{\text{lim}} \approx \pi R_{\text{sh}}^2. \quad (32)$$

The shadow radius for a static observer located at position r_0 is [78]

$$R_{\text{sh}} = r_s \sqrt{\frac{f(r_0)}{f(r_s)}}, \quad (33)$$

where r_s is the photon-sphere radius, determined by the circular null-geodesic condition

$$\left. \frac{d}{dr} \left(\frac{f(r)}{r^2} \right) \right|_{r=r_s} = 0 \implies r_s = \frac{(1-\ell)}{2} \left[3M \pm \sqrt{9M^2 - \frac{8Q^2}{(1-\ell)^3} - \frac{8P^2}{(1-\ell)(1-2\ell)}} \right]. \quad (34)$$

The outer photon sphere corresponds to the plus sign in Eq. (34). For a static observer located at infinity, $r_0 \rightarrow \infty$, the function $f(r_0)$ approaches $1/(1-\ell)$. Therefore, the shadow radius Eq. (33) reduces to

$$R_{\text{sh}} = r_s \sqrt{\frac{1}{(1-\ell)f(r_s)}}. \quad (35)$$

In the Schwarzschild limit $Q = P = \ell = 0$, Eqs. (34) and (35) recover $r_s = 3M$ and $R_{\text{sh}} = 3\sqrt{3}M$, as expected.

Within the coordinate-time normalization adopted in this work, the spectral energy emission rate is [68, 79]

$$\frac{d^2\mathbb{E}}{d\omega dt} = \frac{2\pi^2 \sigma_{\text{lim}}}{e^{\omega/T} - 1} \omega^3, \quad (36)$$

where ω denotes the emitted frequency. Substituting Eq. (35) and using T , we obtain the compact expression

$$\frac{d^2\mathbb{E}}{d\omega dt} = \frac{2\pi^3 R_{\text{sh}}^2 \omega^3}{e^{\omega/T} - 1}. \quad (37)$$

The emission spectrum must therefore be plotted only for parameter choices satisfying both the horizon condition in Eq. (30) and the photon-sphere condition in Eq. (34). Increasing Q , P , or ℓ changes the peak height and the peak position through the combined dependence of T , r_h , and R_{sh} .

The numerical behavior of the thermodynamic and radiative quantities is summarized in Fig. 7. The temperature initially increases with ℓ , reaches a maximum close to the upper part of the allowed interval, and then decreases slightly as the near-extremal regime is approached. The sparsity ratio ψ/ψ_{Sch} is not monotonic: it decreases when the temperature grows, but turns upward again when the temperature starts to drop near the end of the scan. The shadow radius decreases monotonically for the chosen charges, indicating that the optical size of the black hole becomes smaller as positive Lorentz violation increases. The spectral emission rate shows the combined effect of the temperature and the shadow radius: increasing ℓ generally raises the peak and shifts it toward larger $M\omega$ until the variation of T and R_{sh} changes the balance.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we analyzed neutral-particle dynamics, quasiperiodic-oscillation frequencies, Hawking-radiation sparsity, and the spectral energy-emission rate for a dyonic black hole in Lorentz-violating Kalb–Ramond gravity. The spacetime is characterized by the mass M , electric charge Q , magnetic charge P , and Lorentz-violating parameter ℓ . The admissible parameter space is constrained by the existence of the event horizon, Eq. (30), and by the reality of the photon-sphere radius, Eq. (34).

Using the effective-potential formalism, we derived the conditions for circular timelike orbits and wrote the corresponding specific energy and angular momentum in Eqs. (10) and (11). The marginal-stability condition, Eq. (12), determines the ISCO and also coincides with the vanishing of the radial epicyclic frequency. This connection is important for the interpretation of the QPO sector, since only the region with $\Omega_r^2 \geq 0$ corresponds to radially stable circular motion.

For the QPO analysis, we corrected the radial epicyclic frequency so that the Schwarzschild limit is recovered exactly. In this geometry, spherical symmetry implies $\Omega_\theta = \Omega_\phi$, while the periastron-precession frequency is given by $\Omega_p = \Omega_\phi - \Omega_r$ for stable orbits. The conversion to physical frequencies must be performed linearly, $\nu_i = (c^3/2\pi GM)\Omega_i$, rather than by multiplying Ω_i^2 by the same linear factor. The numerical plots use the coordinate-time normalization of the metric; unit normalization at infinity introduces the common factor $\sqrt{1-\ell}$ for frequencies.

In the radiative sector, we obtained the Hawking temperature from $\kappa = f'(r_h)/2$ and $T = f'(r_h)/(4\pi)$ with the coordinate-time normalization used in the metric. For the choice $\mathcal{C}/\tilde{g} = 1$, the sparsity parameter is normalized by $\psi_{\text{Sch}} = 64\pi^3/27$ and differs from the Schwarzschild value through the charge- and Lorentz-violation-dependent factor in Eq. (31). We also corrected the photon-sphere radius and, consequently, the shadow radius entering the high-frequency

absorption cross section and the spectral energy-emission rate.

The numerical figures included in this work make these trends explicit. The effective potential and force profiles show how ℓ reshapes the exterior radial dynamics. The geodesic diagnostics demonstrate that r_+ , r_{ph} , and r_{ISCO} decrease along the positive- ℓ branch for the representative dyonic configuration considered here, while the horizon-existence map shows that the allowed charge domain shrinks as Lorentz violation increases. The QPO plots show that the radial, azimuthal, vertical, and periastron frequencies are modified in the strong-field region, and the radiative plots show correlated changes in T , ψ/ψ_{Sch} , R_{sh} , and $d^2\mathbb{E}/(d\omega dt)$. These combined results indicate that the electric charge, magnetic charge, and Kalb–Ramond Lorentz-violating parameter leave simultaneous imprints on the dynamical and radiative signatures of the black hole.

DATA AVAILABILITY

No new data were generated in this article.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

F.A. acknowledges the Inter University Centre for Astronomy and Astrophysics (IUCAA), Pune, India for granting visiting associateship. E. O. Silva acknowledges the support from Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico (CNPq) (grants 306308/2022-3), Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa e ao Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico do Maranhão (FAPEMA) (grants UNIVERSAL-06395/22), and Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível Superior (CAPES) - Brazil (Finance Code 001).

-
- [1] J. Homan, M. Klein-Wolt, S. Rossi, J. M. Miller, R. Wijnands, T. Belloni, M. van der Klis, and W. H. G. Lewin, *Astrophys. J* **586**, 1262 (2003).
 - [2] M. A. Abramowicz and W. Kluźniak, *Astron. & Astrophys.* **374**, L19 (2001).
 - [3] G. Török, *Astron. & Astrophys.* **440**, 1 (2005).
 - [4] G. Török, M. A. Abramowicz, W. Kluźniak, and Z. Stuchlík, *Astron. & Astrophys.* **436**, 1 (2005).
 - [5] Z. Stuchlík, A. Kotrlová, and G. Török, *Astron. & Astrophys.* **552**, A10 (2013).
 - [6] A. Tursunov, Z. Stuchlík, and M. Kološ, *Phys. Rev. D* **93**, 084012 (2016).
 - [7] M. Kološ, A. Tursunov, and Z. Stuchlík, *Eur. Phys. J C* **77**, 860 (2017).
 - [8] C. Germanà, *Phys. Rev. D* **98**, 083025 (2018).
 - [9] M. Tarnopolski and V. Marchenko, *Astrophys. J* **911**, 20 (2021).
 - [10] M. Kološ, Z. Stuchlík, and A. Tursunov, *Class. Quantum Grav.* **32**, 165009 (2015).
 - [11] Z. Stuchlík, P. Slaný, and G. Török, *Astron. & Astrophys.* **470**, 401 (2007).
 - [12] W. Kluźniak and M. A. Abramowicz, *Astrophys. Space Sci.* **300**, 143 (2005).
 - [13] C. Bambi, *JCAP* **2012** (09), 014.
 - [14] M. Kološ, M. Shahzadi, and Z. Stuchlík, *Eur. Phys. J C* **80**, 133 (2020).
 - [15] M. Shahzadi, M. Kološ, Z. Stuchlík, *et al.*, *Eur. Phys. J C* **82**, 407 (2022).
 - [16] M. Kološ, M. Shahzadi, and A. Tursunov, *Eur. Phys. J C* **83**, 323 (2023).
 - [17] G. Mustafa, S. K. Maurya, P. Channuie, A. Bouzenada, A. Abd-Elmonem, and N. Alhubieshi, *Phys. Dark Univ.* **47**, 101753 (2025).
 - [18] S. K. Maurya, G. Mustafa, A. Ditta, A. Abd-Elmonem, N. Alhubieshi, A. Caliskan, and E. Güdekli, *Phys. Dark Univ.* **47**, 101806 (2025).

- [19] G. Mustafa, F. Javed, S. K. Maurya, A. Abd-Elmonem, F. Atamurotov, N. Alhubieshi, and P. Channuie, *Phys. Dark Univ.* **47**, 101825 (2025).
- [20] K. Akiyama and others (Event Horizon Telescope Collaboration), *Astrophys. J Lett.* **875**, L1 (2019).
- [21] K. Akiyama and others (Event Horizon Telescope Collaboration), *Astrophys. J Lett.* **875**, L2 (2019).
- [22] K. Akiyama and others (Event Horizon Telescope Collaboration), *Astrophys. J Lett.* **875**, L6 (2019).
- [23] K. Akiyama and others (Event Horizon Telescope Collaboration), *Astrophys. J Lett.* **930**, L12 (2022).
- [24] K. Akiyama and others (Event Horizon Telescope Collaboration), *Astrophys. J Lett.* **930**, L16 (2022).
- [25] K. Akiyama and others (Event Horizon Telescope Collaboration), *Astrophys. J Lett.* **930**, L17 (2022).
- [26] B. P. Abbott *et al.*, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **116**, 061102 (2016).
- [27] B. P. Abbott *et al.*, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **119**, 161101 (2017).
- [28] R. Abbott *et al.*, *Astrophys. J Lett.* **896**, L44 (2020).
- [29] J. L. Synge, *MNRAS* **131**, 463 (1966).
- [30] J. M. Bardeen, W. H. Press, and S. A. Teukolsky, *Astrophys. J* **178**, 347 (1972).
- [31] V. A. Kostelecký and S. Samuel, *Phys. Rev. D* **39**, 683 (1989).
- [32] D. Colladay and V. A. Kostelecký, *Phys. Rev. D* **55**, 6760 (1997).
- [33] D. Colladay and V. A. Kostelecký, *Phys. Rev. D* **58**, 116002 (1998).
- [34] D. Colladay and V. A. Kostelecký, *Phys. Lett. B* **511**, 209 (2001).
- [35] V. A. Kostelecký and R. Lehnert, *Phys. Rev. D* **63**, 065008 (2001).
- [36] V. A. Kostelecký and M. Mewes, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **87**, 251304 (2001).
- [37] R. Casana, A. Cavalcante, F. P. Poulis, and E. B. Santos, *Phys. Rev. D* **97**, 104001 (2018).
- [38] J. F. Assuncao, T. Mariz, J. R. Nascimento, and A. Y. Petrov, *Phys. Rev. D* **100**, 085009 (2019).
- [39] F. Ahmed, A. Al-Badawi, and I. Sakalli, *Mod. Phys. Lett. A* **41**, 2650061 (2026).
- [40] F. Ahmed, A. Al-Badawi, I. Sakalli, F. Javed, and S. Kanzi, *Int. J. Geom. Meth. Mod. Phys.* , 2650130 (2026), online first.
- [41] T. Q. Do and W. F. Kao, *Phys. Rev. D* **101**, 044014 (2020).
- [42] W. Liu, D. Wu, and J. Wang, *JCAP* **2024** (09), 017.
- [43] Z.-Q. Duan, J.-Y. Zhao, and K. Yang, *Eur. Phys. J C* **84**, 798 (2024).
- [44] K. Yang, Y.-Z. Chen, Z.-Q. Duan, and J.-Y. Zhao, *Phys. Rev. D* **108**, 124004 (2023).
- [45] L. A. Lessa, J. E. G. Silva, R. V. Maluf, and C. A. S. Almeida, *Eur. Phys. J C* **80**, 335 (2020).
- [46] R. Kumar, S. G. Ghosh, and A. Wang, *Phys. Rev. D* **101**, 104001 (2020).
- [47] R. V. Maluf and C. R. Muniz, *Eur. Phys. J C* **82**, 445 (2022).
- [48] A. Al-Badawi, F. Ahmed, and I. Sakalli, *Phys. Dark Univ.* **50**, 102076 (2025).
- [49] A. Al-Badawi, S. Sanjar, and I. Sakalli, *Eur. Phys. J C* **84**, 825 (2024).
- [50] A. Baruah, Y. Sekhmani, S. K. Maurya, A. Deshamukhya, and M. K. Jasim, *JCAP* **2025** (08), 023.
- [51] W. Liu, D. Wu, and J. Wang, *JCAP* **2025** (05), 017.
- [52] F. M. Belchior, R. V. Maluf, A. Y. Petrov, and P. J. Porfírio, *Eur. Phys. J C* **85**, 658 (2025).
- [53] R. V. Maluf and J. C. S. Neves, *Phys. Rev. D* **103**, 044002 (2021).
- [54] I. Güllü and A. Övgün, *Ann. Phys. (NY)* **436**, 168721 (2022).
- [55] F. Ahmed, A. Al-Badawi, and I. Sakalli, *Phys. Dark Univ.* **52**, 102315 (2026).
- [56] M. Fathi and A. Övgün, *Eur. Phys. J Plus* **140**, 280 (2025).
- [57] Y.-X. Lin, J.-Z. Liu, and Y.-X. Liu, arXiv preprint (2026), arXiv:2605.18371 [gr-qc].
- [58] A. Ashraf, A. Bouzenada, S. K. Maurya, F. Atamurotov, P. Channuie, A. Abd-Elmonem, and N. S. E. Abdalla, *Phys. Dark Univ.* **47**, 101787 (2025).
- [59] G. Mustafa, P. Channuie, F. Javed, A. Bouzenada, S. K. Maurya, A. Cilli, and E. Güdekli, *Phys. Dark Univ.* **47**, 101765 (2025).
- [60] A. Ashraf, A. Ditta, A. Bouzenada, S. K. Maurya, A. Abd-Elmonem, N. A. Suoliman, and P. Channuie, *Phys. Dark Univ.* **48**, 101836 (2025).
- [61] S. Chandrasekhar, *The Mathematical Theory of Black Holes* (Oxford University Press, New York, 1983).
- [62] J. Bicák and Z. Stuchlík, Bulletin of the Astronomical Institutes of Czechoslovakia **27**, 129 (1976).
- [63] Z. Stuchlík and A. Kotrlová, *Gen. Relativ. Gravit.* **41**, 1305 (2009).
- [64] D. N. Page, *Accretion into and Emission from Black Holes*, Ph.D. thesis, California Institute of Technology, Pasadena, California (1976).
- [65] D. N. Page, *Phys. Rev. D* **13**, 198 (1976).
- [66] D. N. Page, *Phys. Rev. D* **14**, 3260 (1976).
- [67] F. Gray, S. Schuster, A. Van-Brunt, and M. Visser, *Class. Quantum Grav.* **33**, 115003 (2016).
- [68] S.-W. Wei and Y.-X. Liu, *JCAP* **2013** (11), 063.
- [69] S. W. Hawking, *Commun. Math. Phys.* **43**, 199 (1975).
- [70] J. D. Bekenstein, *Physical Review D* **7**, 2333 (1973).
- [71] A. Ditta, T. Xu, R. Ali, and G. Mustafa, *Nucl. Phys. B* **994**, 116287 (2023).
- [72] G. Mustafa, A. Ditta, T. Naseer, S. K. Maurya, P. Channuie, A. A. Ibraheem, and F. Atamurotov, *Eur. Phys. J C* **85**, 575 (2025).
- [73] F. Javed, A. Waseem, P. Channuie, G. Mustafa, T. Muhammad, and E. Güdekli, *Phys. Dark Univ.* **47**, 101766 (2025).
- [74] A. Ditta, A. Bouzenada, G. Mustafa, F. Javed, F. Afandi, and A. Mahmood, *Phys. Dark Univ.* **47**, 101818 (2025).
- [75] B. Mashhoon, *Phys. Rev. D* **7**, 2807 (1973).
- [76] C. W. Misner, K. S. Thorne, and J. A. Wheeler, *Gravitation* (W. H. Freeman, San Francisco, 1973).
- [77] N. Sánchez, *Phys. Rev. D* **18**, 1030 (1978).
- [78] V. Perlick and O. Y. Tsupko, *Phys. Rep.* **947**, 1 (2022).
- [79] S. H. Hendi, K. Jafarzade, and B. E. Panah, *JCAP* **2023** (02), 022.